

Constitution of the Reduction Product of Chloral Acetamide

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Meldrum and Bhojraj (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1926, 146) studied the reduction of chloral acid amides having the general formula $R \cdot CO \cdot NH \cdot CHOH \cdot CCl_3$. Yelburgi and Wheeler (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 217)* brought forward evidence to show that the reduction products of these chloral amides had the general formula $R \cdot CO \cdot NH \cdot CH : CCl_2$. The experiments now described confirm Yelburgi and Wheeler's formula. Dichloroethyleneacetamide (II), which is obtained by the reduction of chloral acetamide (I) (Meldrum and Bhojraj, *loc. cit.*), reacts with dry chlorine to give β -trichloro- α -chloroethylacetamide (III) which is also obtained by the action of PCl_5 (1 mol.) on (I). (III) with water gives (I), and with aniline gives (IV).

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Trichloro- α -chloroethylacetamide (III).—Dry chlorine was passed below 60° through a chloroform solution of (II) for 1 hour. Any chloral acetamide, which separated on keeping for two hours, was removed

* (III) and (IV) of Yelburgi and Wheeler's paper (*loc. cit.*, p. 218) should be

and the filtrate was evaporated to yield (III) which was crystallised from dry benzene, m.p. 128° . (III) was also obtained from PCl_5 (1 mol) and (I), the reaction product being treated with petroleum ether to remove POCl_3 . (Found : Cl, 62.6. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{ONCl}_4$ requires Cl, 63.0 per cent).

β -Trichloro- α -anilinoethylacetamide (IV), which was obtained by spontaneous interaction of (III) (3 g.) and aniline (1.5 g.) in benzene, was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 146° . (Found : Cl, 37.4. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 37.8 per cent).

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Condensation of Chloral and Bromal with Polyhydric Alcohols.

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This paper describes the preparations and reactions of the condensation products of chloral and bromal with ethylene glycol and glycerol, and of chloral with erythritol. Bromal is found to be more reactive than chloral.

The results are shown diagrammatically in Figs. 1 and 2.

EXPERIMENTAL.

s-Di-(β -trichloro- α -hydroxy-ethoxy)ethane (I) was prepared by the method of Forcrand (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1889, *iii*, 2, 256).

Anhydrodichloral-glycol (II) was obtained by keeping a solution of (I) in acetic anhydride and a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid for 4 hours and diluting with water or by refluxing a mixture of (I) and acetyl chloride in equal proportions for 30 minutes and pouring into water. (II) separates from alcohol in cubes, m.p. 144° . (Found: Cl, 62.8. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_6$ requires Cl, 62.8 per cent).

It is stable towards hot concentrated nitric acid, boiling alkali solutions and strong ammonia in a sealed tube at 110° . Hot concentrated sulphuric acid changes it back into the original substances.

The diacetyl derivative of (I) (III) was obtained by keeping a